

APPLICATIONS OF ICT IN SCHOOLS AND ITS POTENTIALS IN ENHANCING THE PRACTICES OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become commonplace entities in all parts of life. Across the past twenty years the utilization of ICT has fundamentally changed the practices and systems of virtually all forms of endeavour within education, business and governance. Many significant developments in education systems have happened in recent years, necessitating the update and refinement of teachers' and school administrators' technology abilities. Some of these shifts are the result of changes in government policies about the use of information, communication, and technology (ICT) in schools, while others are the result of advances in cutting-edge pedagogical approaches. The applications of ICT in schools, its potential benefits to the theory and practices of educational management, as well as difficulties linked to ICT integration, are discussed in this paper. It was discovered that ICT expands the flexibility of educational delivery, allowing students to access information at any time and from any location. It has the potential to alter how students are taught and learn because the procedures are now learner-driven rather than teacher-driven. Schools and Educational managers can also use ICT to reach out to underserved communities and new worldwide educational markets. Easy Access to Learning is one of the most important contributions of ICT in the sphere of education. Also, the use of ICT for educational purposes has the potential to enhance the theories and practices of educational management. Some solutions for managing the usage of ICT in schools are presented and explored for school administrators to follow. Based on the conclusion, relevant recommendations were offered.

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Introduction

In all spheres of life, information and communication technology (ICT) have become widespread. Over the last two decades, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) has profoundly altered the practices and procedures of practically every type of company and government endeavor. Education is a very social activity, and great education has always been associated with strong teachers who have a lot of one-on-one time with students.

In the twenty-first century, information and communication technologies (ICTs) have advanced at a breakneck pace. These advancements have had an impact on human efforts, industry processes, and services, including libraries (Aharony, 2014). The introduction of the internet is arguably the most significant and influential development in ICT. The internet currently has a significant impact on a variety of facets of human existence, including relationships, interactions, manufacturing, and service delivery.

With the introduction of mobile devices and social media, internet use has become a way of life for a large portion of the world's population. The proliferation of smart phones, the availability of broadband internet connections, more gadgets with Wi-Fi capabilities, affordability at lower costs, and the availability of broadband internet connections have all contributed to the internet's expansion.

However, according to Pujar and Satyanarayana (2015), "the internet has made a leap ahead from "internet of communication" to "internet of things," allowing devices to be connected and data to be transferred with or without human interaction." Better communication and services were facilitated by the 'internet of communication,' but

only with some human intervention. The 'internet of things' is distinguished by its ability to link items utilizing sensors and networking capabilities with little or no human interaction. Inter-relate with one another in order to attain mutual objectives (Atzori, Iera, and Morabito, 2010).

In the late 1990s and early 2000s, the concept was first brought to the public's attention (Wojcik, 2016). The concept encourages the convergence of a variety of items, including as RFID tags, sensors, actuators, networked devices, and others, which can interact with one another to achieve common goals thanks to unique addressing methods (Atzori et al, 2010).

The concept was considered by Wojcik (2016) as part of the so-called "Future Internet," which is defined as "a dynamic global network infrastructure with self-configuring capabilities based on standard and interoperable communication protocols where physical and virtual "things" have identities, physical attributes, virtual personalities, use intelligent interfaces, and are seamlessly integrated into a single network" (Vermesan et al, 2011). In educational institutions, the internet of things (IoT) provides a lot of potential for better and more efficient services.

Strategies in Applying the Use of ICT to Schools and Educational Management

Managing the usage of school ICT is difficult and necessitates perseverance on the part of all members of an organization. Given the government's huge investment, Educational managers must work in tandem with the government's strategy in controlling and integrating ICT in education. The following are suggested strategies to help design a functional solution in managing school technology:

1. Develop a school ICT policy

The school leaders and educational administrators must have a proper ICT school policy in order to achieve the integration of ICT and technical solutions. The policy serves as a blueprint for the school in developing and implementing a systematic and progressive ICT program for teachers and students.

2. Learn the Technology

The ability of school leaders to use technology is crucial. Leaders who are computer savvy are more aware of the needs of their employees. To improve their computer skills, they must learn the fundamentals of word processing, spreadsheets, presentation software, and how to use a web page and the Internet. A leader must keep up with the latest technologies in order to stay ahead of the competition and become a competitive person. A school leader must be well-versed in current events and technologically aware.

3. Involved others in the Process

Participation literally gives one a sense of belonging and responsibility. All employees should be encouraged to participate in the technology deployment process if it is to be effective. Participation in a change process should be encouraged on a regular basis since it offers individuals participating a sense of control over the process. Teachers should be encouraged to share their technical and pedagogical skills and work in groups to integrate ICT into their classrooms.

4. Enhancing Partnership and Collaboration

Collaboration and partnership can help school administrators improve their technology development and make better decisions. Having a clear vision for technology is also

necessary for making informed decisions about how to integrate and manage ICT in schools. Leaders can establish good partnerships and collaboration with the community, public sector, and corporate sector by developing ICT knowledge and raising funds. In order to promote the accessibility and equity of ICT among students, resourceful leaders should look at a variety of options for purchasing technology resources.

5. Plan a Training Programme for Teachers

Teachers are the nation's builders; they must be adaptable and knowledgeable about current technology. They are the stewards of information diffusion. As a result, a continuous training program for instructors will help them develop a sense of professionalism. The first stage in developing an ICT training program for teachers is inspiring them to learn new information and develop new skills and competences.

To acquire new knowledge and skills in ICT, the schools should:

Set up a team which consists of teachers with varying skills and competencies.

Acquire new inputs from other experts such as teachers from other schools.

Implement a mentoring system to help teachers with minimum skills in ICT.

ICT and Educational Management

ICT expands the flexibility of educational delivery, allowing students to access information at any time and from any location. It has the potential to alter how students are taught and learn because the procedures are now learner-driven rather than teacher-driven. As a result, learners will be better prepared for lifetime learning and learning quality will improve. In addition to geographical flexibility, technology-assisted educational programs eliminate many of the time constraints that learners with special

needs encounter (Moore & Kearsley, 1996). Students are beginning to recognize the value of being able to learn at any time and in any location.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are used in education as a teaching and learning tool as well as an important administrative organization tool. However, there is a problem with the functional integration of ICT in schools especially in school and educational management. The purpose of this study is to investigate school administrators' predispositions toward ICT and the impact of these factors on their usage of ICT in their administrative practices.

Many different ICT application tools have been widely employed in education and management. Computers, the internet, broadcasting technologies (radio and television), and telephony are all available ICT applications for educational administrative reasons. Older technologies, such as the telephone, radio, and television, have a longer and deeper history as teaching aids, although receiving less attention presently. Radio and television, for example, have been utilized for open and distance learning for over forty years.

“School effectiveness is a goal set by administrative leaders through their leadership techniques to help schools achieve particular results across the board,” according to Lin, Xie, Jeng, and Wang (2011). Educational administrators will find it easier to attain their objectives if they use ICT applications. Evidence demonstrates that employing ICT tools such as hardware and software to support their administration and management roles improves teacher work satisfaction (Singh and Munandi, 2012).

The effectiveness of ICT applications depends on good financial management. As a

result, there is a need for administration and management in educational organizations to support financial operations of ICT applications. Esharenana et al (2013), in their work, "highlighted the low rate of ICT adoption and applications in Nigerian Secondary Schools is attributed to several factors, one of which is limited school budget."

Apart from sufficient financial support, data management is also effective part of school headship. It is important that the school maintains accuracy with updated information on all its levels and aspects. In this regard, ICT application helps a lot to keep the records of all levels and aspects of school including students, teachers, staff, and details of meetings' minutes, school publicity, curriculum development materials and entire management information. Moreover, by using ICT application transaction between schools and educational departments will be more direct and efficient, alleviating the manual collection and checking of necessary data and minimizing the duplication of data on school teachers and students (Kawade, 2012).

Easy Access to Learning is one of the most important contributions of ICT in the sphere of education. Students can now obtain e-books, sample examination papers, previous year papers, and other resources through ICT, as well as have simple access to resource persons, mentors, experts, researchers, professionals, and peers from all over the world. This flexibility has increased the availability of just-in-time learning and opened up chances for many more learners who were previously hampered by other obligations (Odumosu, 2013).

Conclusion and Recommendation

ICT adoption and utilization in schools improves teaching, learning, and research.

Despite its success, it's worth noting that not all teachers are skilled or willing to apply it in the classroom, especially in developed countries. In Nigeria, secondary schools have yet to fully utilize them for teaching and learning. Efforts to integrate ICTs into the secondary school system have been largely ineffective. Poor policy and project implementation tactics, as well as a restricted or inadequate information infrastructure, all work against these efforts.

Where new educational strategies based on ICTs provide a different instrument modality. For students, the usage of ICT allows for more personalization of learning. Students have access to tools that adjust to their attention span and provide useful and rapid feedback for literacy advancement in schools where new technologies are used, which is not fully adopted in the Nigerian school system (Umar, 2018).

Based on a qualitative review and analysis of the related literature, it is recommended that administrators increase the use of ICT in their daily administrative tasks to make their tasks more efficient and effective by providing proper technical infrastructure, equipment, and support to ensure the success of ICT applications in the Education System and to grow the knowledge a person has.

Many significant developments in education systems have happened in recent years, necessitating the update and refinement of teachers' and school administrators' technology abilities. Some of these shifts are the result of changes in government policies about the use of information, communication, and technology (ICT) in schools, while others are the result of advances in cutting-edge pedagogical approaches. As technology becomes more readily available in classrooms, many school leaders are confronted with a variety of difficult management concerns.

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